

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

EBT Evaluation Template for **responses to peer review**, for **TEBT-2023-0011**

For evaluating authors' responses to comments provided during peer-review, when the submission is a protocol for a study of any design

Version: 4 Mar 2024

Submission Title	Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical risk assessment with those used in systematic review: research protocol
Submission Reference	TEBT-2023-0011
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin, ORCID 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	
Submission Type	Primary Study Protocol
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.10965795
Status	Accepted
Evaluation Date	18 June 2024
Evaluation Round	Editorial review round 2
Recommendation	Accept
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	Following the second round of peer review, authors have now included their responses to the first round of peer review comments in the manuscript. The revised manuscript has been accepted for publication.

Acceptance note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after assessment in 2 of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

During triage, the handling editor identified some minor issues with the initial submission that could be addressed after peer-review. The manuscript was advanced to peer-review.

During peer-review, the evaluators recommended that further details on the scoping of the two specific fields were needed. The reviewers provided very valuable and detailed comments on the proposed methodology that highlight where detail on specific steps and/or justification for the selection of a specific approach is lacking, including grounding the protocol on a solid up-to-date understanding of methods for consensus building and controlled vocabulary development. Some more fundamental questions were raised about the symmetry of the translation effort and the reciprocity of the exchange between the two communities. The authors addressed these issues by piloting the originally proposed Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method on the document collections. As it did not perform as expected, a new and simpler manual approach has been suggested. As a result, the proposed methods have been amended and simplified.

During the second round of peer review, reviewers expressed their satisfaction with simplified methods. Some issues addressed in responses to reviewers had not been explained in the revised manuscript. It was therefore recommended to also amend the text of the manuscript to improve transparency. The authors did as suggested and submitted the final version of the manuscript which was accepted.

The following points of scientific interest were surfaced by the review process; first, piloting planned methods whenever feasible is worthwhile exercise that may lead to simpler, improved methods, secondly, the perspective of reviewers from other academic disciplines on similar issues was very useful and allowed authors to benefit from experience gained in those disciplines.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at [10.5281/zenodo.10452191](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10452191).